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DESIGN HARVESTS: A NETWORK OF SOCIAL COLLABORATIVE INNOVATION HUBS

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ABSTRACT

The paper introduces an innovative social collaborative design project: “Design Harvests”—Design for Xian Qiao sustainable rural community in Chongming. The goal of this project is to create prototypes of sustainable rural-urban interaction and development based on the usage of local resources and strengths. One of the most important proposals is to establish a network of innovation hubs together with the local community. Each innovation hub will be a platform of promoting a series of sustainable design solutions for local development. More over, it will incubate and demonstrate new business models based on the resources of the rural communities and interaction between urban and rural. Meanwhile, a systematic network is designed and formed among the hubs to have holistic and systemic impacts throughout the whole territory. The key principle of this project is co-creation and interdiscipline. Enabling the local community through social collaboration is one of the main tasks of this project. Social collaboration in this project is not only the cooperation among different stakeholders such as government, enterprises, designers and communities but also among different disciplines such as economics, sociology, engineering and design. To conclude, the paper summarizes the methodology used in this project and explores more possibilities of how design can contribute to such a kind of social collaborative process.

Keywords: rural development, social innovation, local heritages

INTRODUCTION: A BALANCED PERSPECTIVE FOR URBAN/RURAL DEVELOPMENT

Developing countries are challenging laboratories for innovative communities that have to deal with existing evolving scenarios that consist of many interconnected parts, often structured in an incoherent and disharmonic way.

The Chinese context, in particular, is one of the most critical, because of the rapidity of the growth and the massive changes in the socio-economic system that consists in a mainly massive migration from the rural countryside to urban areas. One of the main impacts of the high speed economic growth in China is the structure of urbanization and the resettlement of the balance between metropolis and rural areas; the countryside is not considered attractive any more, and moving to big cities seems to be the only way to reach progress and development, as a mix of better education, better health care services, higher income and modern lifestyle.

In previous publications we discussed a very typical Chinese metaphor to compare the rural-urban system with the Yin and Yang, where two interdependent elements, each with specific characteristics, can strengthen one another to create a harmonious system (Lou, Diaz, 2009; Jegou, 2010). This image clearly entwines that sustainable development of China cannot leave aside the pursuit of a rural-urban balance, and this is obviously a complex relationship because the new urbanism affects the rural areas deeply and involves transformation of the communities. Moreover, the design can approach this balance reconstruction process aiming to keep the value of both the system and enhance the

interaction among them.

China, and Shanghai on the main stage, declared to the world during the Expo 2010 proposals of new possible shapes for the city of the future, and indeed the drive for progress and the swiftness of policy implementation in China permit experimentation with new ideas and methods. The phenomenon of urbanization in China has been widely analyzed and comprehensively documented through implementation of various project and urban plans like the “nine cities nine town” or the planning related to ecological new cities. Emerging from that is the Chinese model, whose implementation aims to be a concrete solution for new form of urbanism, in order to reduce the pressure of development on the metropolis and to extend the economic benefits to periurban areas. (De Hartog, 2010). Nevertheless, without specifically evaluate the urban planning impact and meaning of these plans, is more and more clear that more sustainable forms of urban planning are being sought and envisioned, including the consideration of several community oriented concerns: the identity related issues, an improvement of capillarity of economic streams and revenues, a balanced distribution of work force and social facilities through wider groups of society. Is this is the framework space in which design can intervene through practical action in which the role of people and community is balanced with the need of the expansion by the city side.

In the Yin/Yang perspective surely urbanization sprawl is not the only solution, and is even not a solution at all. Development directions shall require the balance between urban and rural according to the idea of reciprocal and mutual strengths. From a very design perspective we think the local community should be involved in sustainable development strategies with the aim of restoring urban-rural balance in the area, by promoting between the two entities dialogue and exchanges. The challenge, for the designer of systems and services, is to stabilize China’s growth by fostering ways in which people can sustain themselves, economically, environmentally, and socially. In meeting this challenge, it will be necessary to involve the intended beneficiaries: only thus can general principles be adapted to local conditions and proposed solutions be made truly sustainable.

OUR LOCAL FIELD EXPERIMENT AT CHONGMING ISLAND

To go deeper in the tentative experiment on this topic we are building a living prototype of yin/yang balance relationship. Shanghai offers interesting cases because the city is surrounded by farming fields and agriculture based areas. In particular, a 1300 square meter and 600000 habitants island, Chongming Dao, located at the mouth of Yangtze River Delta, can be defined as a “rururban” area (Donadieu, 1998), located in the periurban zone of Shanghai, but with the characteristics of a typical, qualified rural landscape. This territory shares the same challenges with most of the rural areas in China, but most relevant, here, are the socio-economic problems connected with rapid urbanization. Young and educated people are leaving for the city, together with men looking for decent employment; for this reason most of the residents on the island are old, female and poorly educated. The income that is made from jobs in the village (mainly farming and government factory work) is very low, and there are no facilities for leisure or cultural activities. The slow life in the island is considered boring, and local potential (healthy environment, craft, typical products, skills etc.) is not seen as a sufficient resource to make the island attractive. The unattractiveness of the rural lifestyle for many has led to the loss of human and economic resources. Chongming Island’s unique positioning within the city is one of the reasons for these problems, but also makes it an excellent venue for experiment the nature of this imbalance and possibly identify virtuous actions of sustainable implementation.

Figure. 1, a view of Chongming Island and Shanghai bay

On this island we chose a typical village, the XianQiao village, to start up the project. The Chongming Sustainable Community Project is a design research initiative led by Tongji University and Studio TAO, an urban design “think-and-action tank” focused on sustainability, that is the research partner and investor; supported by DESIS-China, and involving since from the beginning, a growing and heterogeneous network of local and international partners, from several universities that cooperative through students creativity and entrepreneurial workshops, as well as companies that are trying to open new business on service markets, still pretty poor in the Chinese context. The research project network directly involves several participants, including the local government of Chongming Island, village communities, business partners and university resources. The Chongming initiative seeks to use diffused design actions as a strategy specifically to promote solutions toward a sustainable future for rural China. The project has two cores, a deep and analytical research plan and a specific small-scale infrastructure investment between agriculture and service facilities. The research plan developed a thick full-scale knowledge of the local context, in order to outline the system of resources that are more promising for valorization. The results of the research have been disseminated in Cumulus conference during the last

years and in a forthcoming book (Lou, Diaz, Valsecchi 2011).

All the specific research activities have been developed according to a general methodology framework; in order to verify and implement a solutions model based on resource exchanges between rural and urban, a vision of the island as a open knowledge system is utilized, and the research phases gradually explore this knowledge. The following schema summarizes the research process describing the different steps in which knowledge is discovered, explored and fostered.

Figure. 2, a summary schema of local values based intervention on rural area

In the first step we looked for potential resources, among which we can identify major and more relevant strengths. We discovered that what we can rely as local strengths is not necessarily unique and special kind of features, but they are mostly hidden, as well as the corresponding weakness in simple ordinary processes and activities within the local context. In the case of Chongming we found for example two interesting directions that are currently included in the implementation phase. The first direction is the handicrafts system of the island, that currently refers to a spontaneous flow of tradition and knowledge, underestimated as a local resource and economic gear, even it represents a diffused and spread activity. Another example is the value system related to kitchen, as a place, that in Chongming are typical and traditionally equipped, but also as a system of values more generally connected with the food chain; so is around the kitchen in the village as physical undesigned spaces that more conversation

and envisioning can be done, to relate the food production and the agriculture techniques, with the food consumption and habits, through the food lifecycle.

Starting from these enhanced topics we proceed with the concept implementations, following the approach to narrow down to the specific actions and then to collect and connect from their impact the benefit for the whole system. A way to clarify and make this benefit concrete is to transform the knowledge we acquired from the system in tangible outcomes from the system itself. Through branding we intend to create and disseminate material identity artifacts and products, involving the island and their habitants in a conscious bottom up process of self-recognition and enhancement.

Beside the knowledge base, investment has been necessary to give a practice oriented destination to our research, in order to be able to prototype our intervention inside a living existing heritage; the prototype includes the construction of a community centre in the village, surrounded by a field for organic agriculture experiments with the local farmers.

Accordingly, the Chongming Sustainable Community Project aims to network villages on the island to Shanghai through business and communication exchanges based on and driven by community decisions. Residents live as they like, without sacrificing their sense of place. Design is the key tool to be used in this project to interconnect the various souls within Shanghai, fostering sustainability by allowing people to regenerate a system benefiting their own localities. Thus, the immediate purpose of this strategy is attending to the micro level particulars, but within a holistic, macro-level vision, and to develop a series of scenario-building prototypes. As the Chongming project seeks above all to create productive new exchanges and interactions among some of Shanghai's many diverse social groups and constituencies, the end result may not always be physical development as in new infrastructure, but rather the development of the immaterial connections among people, and the exploration of their possibilities.

ISLAND SCENARIOS

Several scenarios have been derived from the

research, and the current phase of start up of the implementation make us to include them in the business model evaluation. The scenes depicted allow us to discuss the quality of scenario with the local communities and they will be the definitive contributors in the future implementation. So a central market has been imagined, located in an abandoned village factory along a tourism route, with the factory being renovated to house the market and can include activities space related to agriculture, rural education, arts and leisure. Universities can use the spaces for research and workshop, thereby a higher education presence can be established on the island. Community gardens on the factory grounds can be cultivated by the villagers and city visitors, thus helping to build relationships. Various arts venues are also planned, to showcase local and city artists and further promote the mutually beneficial coexistence of urban and rural populations. Hopefully but easily these various initiatives will create jobs in running and maintaining the different facilities involved. These are topic of discussion, in the shape of design artifacts, maps, users scenario, system maps, storyboards, cultural probes, that we share with our partners, community members, government agencies, businesses and designers. Within this macro opportunity areas a system of frame-working projects is now in the development phase; material and immaterial solutions have been visualized, prototyped and modified several times, since each solution is left open to new opportunities, new business possibilities, and local initiatives.

In Chongming we are implementing a large scale networked, participatory process. The project has the potential to reshape the urban-rural relationship, emphasizing the various sustainabilities—economic, environmental, and social—by which alone contemporary Chinese society will continue to develop over the long term. The ultimate objective of this approach, therefore, is to extend the design process into society by soliciting the active participation of all stakeholders in developing solutions to design problems. It is hoped that the holistic, systematic approach described here can help overcome the old oppositions of urban and rural, government and community; local and global that have complicated and hindered Chinese

development up to this point. As the Yin/ Yang philosophy reveals, these entities are all equal forces, equally necessary for sustainable change. The challenge of design in its newly expanded role is to elicit solutions, in a context of rapid change, in a balanced and inclusive way.

Therefore we are producing during the time an open set of research tools, with the aim to transform them in as well open set of products and services and knowledge as a benefit for the community. The hub contains all the conceptual facilities to sustain the purpose that the dialogue between the heterogeneous communities and the local society must be dynamic during all the duration of the projects. The scenarios produced should not only be designed starting by local specificities, but also be able to increase the value of territorial resources and involve in a proactive way the local community in a bottom-up approach. We envision the island as a system of values, and we are not intended to give back them solutions, but the possibility to envision as well this system, and to contribute to them as main actor. All the Chinese trend of new urban development and rural qualification show projects that make a breakthrough changing in the traditional design of the city in China, but at the same time they try to preserve and reinterpret that features connected to the locality.

Through a collaborative effort involving multi-disciplinary teams, knowledge is being generated relevant to improving the outlook for this island and its people in the coming decades. The vision for this project is to make a specifically Chinese example of how to practice ecological sustainability, while simultaneously improving daily life and socioeconomic opportunities within a rural community. A successful outcome in Chongming will serve as a prototype for using the design process to improve human life, in China and beyond.

FROM THE LOCAL TO THE SYSTEM

Producing a real change in the local context, especially in a close-knit community, is possible just when the solutions are generated from a deep analysis of all the aspects of the context, and developed with the participation of the community itself. In this way each sub-project will face specific problems, needs and expectations of the users.

Even when supported by a heterogeneous network of partners, it is impossible for the design team to face the complexity of the system as a whole, and be detail-oriented at the same time. The acupuncture design approach is used in the strategic planning of the project to create that systemic effect that can help regulate the system holistically towards a sustainable direction.

An acupuncture design approach, allows the designer to work on small different micro projects in synergy, producing a systemic effect (Jégou, 2010). It has been already applied in the urban planning field, as a decentralized approach that uses a grid to bring out the distinctive quality of each neighborhood, in which selective intervention can ease problems in the broader urban fabric. (LeDantec 1991).

In the Chongming project one of the strategic functions of the Hub as a platform, is to aggregate and coordinate the local network of projects, centralizing some of the functions and enhancing the communication among different stakeholders. The model of the hub as a platform to incubate new creative opportunities for local sustainable development, open to the local community that is involved in the implementation of small subproject, can be applied to different contexts. What changes is the context, and therefore the specific vocation of the hub.

The second Innovation Hub has already been built in Liangping, Sichuan province: a sustainable elementary school funded by China-US Center for Sustainable Development and the Liangping Government.

The design project has been carried out with the final aim of creating an eco-sustainable building that interacts with local nature, culture and society. The school, that is structured to maximize the students' interaction with their environment, is also open to the local community. The specific vocation of this second hub, in fact, is the education about sustainability, which is provided not just to kids but also to their families. Through small local initiatives connected to the school it is possible also here to apply the acupuncture holistic effect to the system. With the same criteria new Innovation Hubs will be built in other places in China, each one with specific characteristics and a clear vocation; these local platforms will be all linked to each other, in a

network where communication and exchange of resources are encouraged.

Analyzing the connection between the local and global scale in the two ways, different implications in the interaction can be found.

- From the local to the net: each node contributes in the shaping of the net and its characteristics, which are evolving according to the evolutions of the different contexts.
- From the net to the local: the organization of the different contexts in a macro-layer helps in reinforcing and adds value to local resources, underused until that moment t

DISSEMINATION IN THE NETWORK

As we previously mentioned, the key strategic issue in the DESIGNHarvests process is the involvement of an evolving network of partners in the different stages of the process.

The potential of a multidisciplinary approach in facing complex situations can be better understood contextualizing it in the networking society framework. The EMUDE research (2006) has underlined that designers have to consider themselves as a part of “a complex mesh of design networks (...) of individual people, enterprises, non-profit organizations, local and global institutions that are using their creativity and entrepreneurship to solve problems, to open new possibilities and, sometimes, to take some concrete steps towards sustainability” (Manzini, 2006).

When dealing with a context related systemic project, the designer should be able to involve these actors in the research and idea generation phase, creating a dynamic and flexible innovative community that can contribute to the creation of forward-looking potential solutions. Along the entire activity course the shape of the network, the members of the community, and their tasks and interests can change, according to the characteristics of each step, and following the directions that the process may take.

For all these reasons, a relevant part of the research team is the activity of dissemination of information through different channels, both local and international. In the past three years lectures,

workshops, events have been organized, and all the documentation related to the project has been published in different media.

It is not common, especially in the Chinese reality to use the service design approach to face complex situations related to the local development.

Involving a heterogeneous international network of partners is a way to enhance the circulation of information, insights and ideas, in a continuous exchange process that promotes the diffusion of innovative solutions.

The newness, that is the main characteristic of every innovative solution, implies that some degree of uncertainty is involved, and so a lack of structure in the message is normally to be expected.

Inside our network raw working material is often shared, and members of the informal community can take it, transform it and make other processed information circulate; this is what happened with different workshops and sub-project that used DESIGN Harvests as a framework.

Disseminating the innovation and share the material along the network links allow us to connect resources spanning different sets of dissimilar groups in a system.

CONCLUSIONS

The research background of the project is the Rural-Urban relationship, and how it can affect local development.

A sustainable development can be achieved just when the rural and the urban find a balance. This balance is promoted, in the DESIGN Harvests project, through a practice based research, that, using the previously described methodology, seeks the potential of the context and involves the community in the co-creation of a system of micro-projects that can enhance a systemic change.

Testing ideas on the real context by creating rapid prototypes of services is necessary to enhance local participation. “Designers can be facilitators or mediators but also triggers. They can operate as members of a co-design team, collaborating with a well-defined group of final users, or as design activists, launching socially meaningful design initiatives.” (Manzini, Rizzo 2011)

One of the main difficulties in this part of the

process is the communication with locals. Different tools have been developed, to get over language and cognitive barriers.

In November 2010 a small market of local products has been organized, during an event that took to Xianqiao around 300 visitors from the city. Farmers were skeptical and didn't want to be directly involved in this experience. The solution was to buy products from those farmers, spend some time close to their houses, to rebrand them and repackage them (so that they could see the whole process), and then sell the products at the market during the event.

This prototype of the experience was not useful to test the success of the initiative itself, but can be mainly seen as a communication tool between the design group and the possible rural co-creator.

Around the market stall conversations have been engaged and feedback and opinions have been collected.

Another initiative that we couldn't realize as we wanted is the "Community Garden" on the island. In February 2011 we started going to Chongming relatively often, to initiate a small community garden that was supposed to be owned by a community of people leaving in Shanghai. Since it was pretty tough to collect a group of motivated people to go to Chongming on a weekly base just to check on the field, we decided to make a trial version of the garden on one terrace in Shanghai.

Xiao Chongming as a real scale prototype to study the interaction, learn how to and start a conversation with city users.

It is useful because it makes the garden accessible to the possible users and allows the research team to focus on the process, and be directly involved on a daily base.

The importance of rapid prototyping of solutions and direct involvement in the local community (also on a personal scale) are two key learnings that have been empirically proved.

Although design for sustainable development always focuses on small context, to develop solutions targeted to the specific case, explicability is an issue that is always taken into consideration for future developments. Chongming Island is the local context where we carried out our research activity, but the

goal is to create, in the next future, more Innovation Hubs, each with a specific vocation, in different parts of China.

This network of Hubs will also be connected to the international interdisciplinary community. New possibilities to face the macro-system complexity can in this way emerge, reaching macro-transformation as a result of a synergy of micro-project with an acupuncture approach.

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